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D7.2

Dissemination Material

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RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

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Author(s) – in alphabetical order		
Name	Organisation	E-mail
David Quesada	ENIDE	David.quesada@enide.com
J.Vicent Pastor	ENIDE	Jvicent.pastor@enide.com
Francesc Rosinés	ENIDE	Francesc.rosines@enide.com

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
EC	European Commission
PO	Project officer
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

Logistics clusters become value creators for the regions where they are formed, where a mix of good intermodal connections, logistics platforms and large freight volumes are in place. Well-established logistics clusters still do not leverage their full potentials in terms of competitiveness and sustainability for the European industry and society, due to several reasons:

- Not enough coordination between the local actors in the cluster,
- Not enough connectivity and coordination between European logistics clusters to maximize the full network potential of the clusters and related hubs.

Moreover, logistics clusters also need to deal and minimize negative impacts such as congestion, noise, land use and local pollution.

Following the main project objective that is to enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of the Clusters, a lot of efforts is needed to make them aware of new possibilities and concepts, including enabling them to take part of Clusters networks and corridors' flows. These efforts include a variety of dissemination actions leading to understanding benefits resulting from the innovative solutions being developed.

The objective of this document is to present a number of dissemination materials communicating to stakeholders the main project idea, vision and ambition in order to create impact by raising awareness around CLUSTERS 2.0.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose of Document

This document presents a number of dissemination materials produced to communicate to stakeholders the project concept and get the target audience with CLUSTERS 2.0 solutions.

2.2 Intended audience

This document is addressed to the Consortium members.

3. General Dissemination Objectives

3.1 Background

The overall aim of the CLUSTERS 2.0 dissemination framework is to promote the project, its mission and results to a wide range of stakeholders at European, national, regional and local levels. It is important to communicate with a far-reaching audience and each level of governance has different stakeholders which CLUSTERS 2.0 needs to address. Therefore, the project will adopt a cross-level dissemination approach.

The project also aims to establish the project and its tools as a reference point among interested Clusters and industries stakeholders in logistics overall. This aspect is increasingly important for the legacy of the project and aims to encourage the actual take-up and deployment of the CLUSTERS 2.0 solution after the project has finished.

A key objective of CLUSTERS 2.0 is to develop effective communication interfaces and dissemination channels. All dissemination tools will have a clear message and explain the objectives and mission of the project in a consistent and coherent way.

The project will also communicate the role of the EU and the H2020 Programme through all the dissemination channels. Furthermore, special emphasis will be given to feeding useful outputs to future relevant projects.

3.2 Objectives

The main goal of this document is to get the project partners with the main initial material available to attract a number of stakeholders, in particular Industries, with the project and involve them in the project actions.

The primary objectives regarding the production of the project dissemination materials are to provide tools to create awareness around the solutions developed, establish and maintain a favourable reputation of the project and promote the project concept and proposed solutions.

More specifically:

- Attract stakeholders to the project concept.
- Promote understanding of the benefits that CLUSTERS 2.0 will bring.
- Promote Innovations in Logistics: create understanding that sustainability requires collaboration of logistics market players and research and how they may be affected by the project solutions.
- Encourage participation: Promote active participation of stakeholders in the development of CLUSTERS 2.0 solutions and in knowledge-sharing.

The dissemination materials allow us to present basic information on the project to the community of our interest and attract them with the project concept.

4. Dissemination materials

4.1 Project logo

To give CLUSTERS 2.0 a common image towards the outside world and to communicate it in a consistent way with a clear and recognisable brand, a project logo and an overall project identity has been created.

A Microsoft Word and PowerPoint template using the CLUSTERS 2.0 project identity has also been created, which will be used by all members of the consortium for presentations, written deliverables, etc.

A graphic charter has also been created which is a comprehensive document that outlines the presentation rules for the graphic elements that convey the project's visual identity. This will be used for reports, designing the website and also PowerPoint presentations.

Figure 1. Project logo

4.2 Project flyer

A project leaflet and a postcard have been designed, which will present the project's main objectives and expected results at a glance and explain the CLUSTERS 2.0 approach. It will target a wide range of stakeholders and will be the project's identity card to the outside world. The initial leaflet will be in English, and the printed versions will be available for conferences, fairs, seminars and so on. The leaflet could also be printed in other languages for national take-up seminars.

Project flyers will be printed in a number enough to distribute to all project partners, which will use in his day-to-day with clients and other projects. In addition, a number of copies will be printed for distribution in events and workshops, but bearing in mind that updated versions will be produced. The current estimation is as follows:

Date	Estimated number of copies
M1	200 (postcard)
M5	1500
M12	1000
M24	1000
M30	1000

Figure 1. Project flyer – front page & back page

"If we want to reach the EU objective on modal shift for all transportation beyond 300 km and attract and strengthen competitiveness of local industries at the same time, we need to drive the development of an open collaborative network of hyper connected logistics multimodal clusters building on Ten-T", CLUSTERS 2.0

Duration: 1 May 2017 - 30 April 2020
Total cost: 6.329.618,75€
EC contribution: 5.998.743,75€
Coordinator: PTV Planung Transport Verkehr AG;
Coordinator: Marcel Huschebeck, PTV Group, marcel.huschebeck@ptvgroup.com
Dissemination: Francesc Rosinés, ENIDE, francesc.rosines@enide.com
www.clusters20.eu info@clusters20.eu [@clusters20_EU](https://twitter.com/clusters20_EU)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723265.

Figure 2. Project flyer – the inside

Figure 3. Project postcard – front

Figure 4. Project postcard – back

4.3 General project presentation

The general project presentation is an electronic presentation comprising of few slides introducing the main project idea. This presentation will be available to all Consortium Partners and will be used by the Consortium to present and promote CLUSTERS 2.0 and its results. It will be progressively updated in line with the project's achievements and adapted according to the audience.

A Microsoft Word and PowerPoint template using the CLUSTERS 2.0 project identity has also been created, which will be used by all members of the consortium for presentations, written deliverables, etc.

Figure 6. General Project Presentation

4.4 Roll-up and Posters

In order to establish the visibility of CLUSTERS 2.0 at major logistics conferences, CLUSTERS 2.0 roller banners have been produced. They will be produced in English. They will also be used to give a common visual identity to the events that CLUSTERS 2.0 organises itself.

A printed version will be produced in M5 / M6 in order to be used in Autumn 2017 events, additional printed copies are planned during first year of the project. Updated versions and its printed material are planned in M20 and M30.

Figure 7. Example of Project roll-up

4.5 Project videos

A series of short videos will be produced during the lifetime of the project to communicate general project mission, main objectives and structure, as well as outcomes to various categories of audiences. These will be displayed on the project's website and other easily accessible e-media (i.e. YouTube).

The following dates are estimated for the different videos:

Video	Date
Video 1. Short video	M8
Video 2. Short video	M20
Video 3. Results video	M29

4.6 Press releases

Press releases will be produced periodically, in line with the progression of the project to inform about the outputs and all upcoming CLUSTERS 2.0 events. For this end, the Project Coordinator and the Partners responsible for the main deliverables will inform the WP6 Partners on the content to be disseminated. The press releases will be issued through selected EU and international agencies and will be sent to all identified media contacts specialised in logistics.

See a template of Press Release applied to Clusters 2.0 KoM in Annex I.

A press release will be produced every time an important milestone or event is performed.

4.7 Newsletter

Twice a year, a newsletter will be issued to ensure that all stakeholders are regularly updated on project's developments. It will be circulated to the project and partner networks. Target groups will be segmented and regular analysis will be driven on newsletter results to optimise the impact.

Number	Due date
E-newsletter 1	October 2017
E-newsletter 2	April 2018
E-newsletter 3	October 2018
E-newsletter 4	April 2019
E-newsletter 5	October 2019

5. On-line tools

In this section, several on-line tools are reviewed. Then, an analysis of the potential use of them to the objectives related to the CLUSTERS 2.0 internet community presence is done; the final goal is to select the most suitable ones, defining the potential use of them.

5.1 Web site

A specific website for the project has been created (www.clusters20.eu and www.clusters20.com). The design of this website is in line with CLUSTERS 2.0 visual identity. This website provides an excellent overview of the project and is continuously updated with latest news and events related to CLUSTERS 2.0. The website displays a concise description of the project's objectives and expected results, including the CLUSTERS 2.0 Living labs. Visitors will find information about latest project developments, public upcoming and past relevant events related to CLUSTERS 2.0 and the list of all the partners involved, thus reinforcing the image and representativeness of the project.

All published CLUSTERS 2.0 articles and project materials will be available for download directly from the website. This will also include a summary of selected deliverables drafted by the respective WP leaders with the results and findings that are to be made public.

Visitors may already get in touch directly with partners and/or with the project through the Contact section for any enquiry related to the project.

The website is managed by the Dissemination Coordinator, who is the primary contact for partners wishing to add content to the website. Partners are expected to contribute with relevant information related to CLUSTERS 2.0 activities and outcomes relevant for CLUSTERS 2.0 publication on the website. This information shall be sent to the Dissemination Coordinator, who will check the appropriateness of the content for publication on the website. If necessary the Dissemination Coordinator will liaise with other partners before publishing.

A website has been created for the project CLUSTERS 2.0. The following addresses have been assigned to the project:

- WWW.CLUSTERS20.EU
- WWW.CLUSTERS20.COM

Below, several screenshots show pages from the website. However the dynamic behaviour of the site is only appreciated by visiting it.

Clusters 2.0 [Homepage](#) [The Project](#) [News](#) [Deliverables](#) [Contact](#)

CLUSTERS 2.0

IT WILL USE AN OPEN NETWORK OF LOGISTICS CLUSTERS OPERATING IN THE FRAME OF THE OPEN LOGISTICS CLUSTERS CONCEPT TO ADDRESS THE LOCAL IMPACTS SUCH AS CONGESTION, NOISE, LAND USE AND LOCAL POLLUTION LEVELS

THE VISION OF CLUSTERS 2.0

CO-ORDINATION
Enhancing and advancing towards a better co-ordination between legislative actions in clusters

CONNECTIVITY
Improving co-ordination and connectivity between European legislative clusters

OPEN
Making optimal use of an Open Network of Logistics Clusters

CLUSTERS 2.0 WILL LEVERAGE THE FULL POTENTIAL OF EUROPEAN LOGISTICS CLUSTERS FOR A SUSTAINABLE, EFFICIENT AND FULLY INTEGRATED TRANSPORT SYSTEM

LIVING LABS OF CLUSTERS 2.0

LIVING LABS OF CLUSTERS 2.0

WHAT WILL CLUSTERS 2.0 PROVIDE?

GOODSTREAM
Establishing Goodstream's European wide community for freight sharing and with location dependent rates

ASSET MANAGEMENT
Optimized hardware and asset management through real time services at depots and terminals

NEW LOADING UNITS
Developing New Modular Loading Units and innovative handling and terminalisation technology to streamline handling processes within clusters for road and intermodal modes

GOVERNANCE MODELS
Novely developed governance models introducing the role of a neutral agent forming the basis for each business model

ENHANCED SERVICES
Enhanced services on the supply side introducing the concept of Proximity Terminal Technology (PTT) enabled by enhanced information and asset management

REGULATION
Regulation and policy enhancing the safety of collaborative cluster environments

THE PARTNERS OF CLUSTERS 2.0

THE PARTNERS OF CLUSTERS 2.0

MEET THE TEAM OF CLUSTERS 2.0

<p>MARCO HÜBNER, CLUSTER COMMUNITY COORDINATOR Manager at PTV Group, Terminal Technology</p>	<p>MASSIMO RICCI, COORDINATION COORDINATOR Innovation Director at ENIDE</p>	<p>NICOLA MARCELLINI, LEADER, INNOVATION MANAGEMENT CEO at European Strategy</p>	<p>CHIARA LORENZI, LEADER, CLUSTER COMMUNITY COORDINATION PTT, PTC coordinator for Innovation Europe Area</p>
<p>DR. PETR VÁCLAVÍK, LEADER, BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT, LOGISTIC CLUSTERS Head of Innovation Division at PTV</p>	<p>ALESSIO BERTOLDINI, LEADER, NEW LOGISTICS CLUSTER COMMUNITY COORDINATION Business Development at PTV</p>	<p>STEFANO PAVIA, LEADER, CLUSTER COMMUNITY COORDINATION CEO of INNOVATION</p>	<p>NICOLA MARCELLINI, LEADER, REGULATORY AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT CEO of Innovation PT Technology</p>

Clusters 2.0

CLUSTERS 2.0 PARTNERS

PTV GROUP, enide, mosaiclect, P&G, CONSORZIO INNOVATION

CLUSTERS 2.0 PROJECT OFFICE MEETING

5.1 LinkedIn

Description

LinkedIn is a social networking website for people in professional occupations. Founded in December 2002 and launched on May 5, 2003, it is mainly used for professional networking. As of April 2017, LinkedIn had 500 million members in 200 countries. LinkedIn has been described by online trade publication *TechRepublic* as having "become the de facto tool for professional networking".

LinkedIn also supports the formation of interest groups. Groups support a limited form of discussion area, moderated by the group owners and managers. Groups keep their members informed through emails with updates to the group, including most talked about discussions within your professional circles. Groups may be private, accessible to members only or may be open to Internet users in general to read, though they must join in order to post messages.

Use

LinkedIn, given its professional focus, is seen as one important method for the awareness creation concerning CLUSTERS 2.0 project. Even more, the group concept seems perfect in order to support the activities for the creation and managing of an interest group related to project goals.

So, a LinkedIn group will be created. It will focus on Clusters and Physical Internet issues and, although it will promote mainly the activities and results coming from CLUSTERS 2.0, it will not be limited to this, including also additional contents and news from other related activities, such as conferences, projects and so. The topics for discussion will be: Clusters' performance, clusters' collaboration, corridors, modular logistics units, connectivity, etc.

The contents generated in the other tools will be also promoted here: newsletters, project events, public results, etc. Moreover, the potential discussion created in this forum will be analysed in order to have additional feedback on the project strategy.

It will be initially promoted in several different ways, including the website, the consortium, the EHLIG (European High Level Industry Group) and other known stakeholders.

Created LinkedIn group: Clusters 2.0

5.2 Twitter

Description

According Wikipedia, Twitter is an online social networking service and microblogging service that enables its users to send and read text-based messages of up to 140 characters, known as "tweets". As of 2016, Twitter had more than 319 million monthly active users.

Tweets are publicly visible by default, but senders can restrict message delivery to just their followers. Users can tweet via the Twitter website, compatible external applications (such as for smartphones), or by Short Message Service (SMS) available in certain countries.

As a social network, Twitter revolves around the principle of followers. When you choose to follow another Twitter user, that user's tweets appear in reverse chronological order on your main Twitter page. If you follow 20 people, you'll see a mix of tweets scrolling down the

Clusters 2.0

page: breakfast-cereal updates, interesting new links, music recommendations, even musings on the future of education.

A word, phrase or topic that is tagged at a greater rate than other tags is said to be a trending topic. Trending topics become popular either through a concerted effort by users or because of an event that prompts people to talk about one specific topic. These topics help Twitter and their users to understand what is happening in the world.

Twitter is ranked as one of the ten-most-visited websites worldwide by Alexa's web traffic analysis.

Use

In the case of Twitter, given its broadcasting power as well as the flexible connections that could be established, it is seen as key method for the promotion of the contents produced at the project scope. Beyond the number of users, the average profile is focus on adult people, even if this is an open group. Also, although it is used in a social and open way, many users already use it as a professional tool, using the right hash tags matching their interests, as a focus news feed.

At the same, it allows a kind of open discussion concerning the topics of the project. On the one hand, this is a useful communication channel with the audience of the project, however, it can be also a potential risk, allowing third parties to easily interfere in the right message.

As in the other cases, the contents generated in the other tools will be also promoted here: newsletters, project events, public results, etc. It is foreseen that this platform could be the natural starting point to CLUSTERS 2.0 for many.

It will be initially promoted in several different ways, including the website, the consortium, the EHLIG and other known stakeholders. Also, an active role of the project account will be of the great value: discussing and complementing the existing related twitter accounts in order to create interest in the project goals.

Twitter account: @Clusters20_eu

5.3 Youtube

Description

YouTube is a video-sharing website, created by three former PayPal employees in February 2005, on which users can upload, view and share videos. The company is based in San Bruno, California, and uses Adobe Flash Video and HTML5 technology to display a wide variety of user-generated video content, including movie clips, TV clips, and music videos, as well as amateur content such as video blogging, short original videos, and educational videos.

Most of the content on YouTube has been uploaded by individuals, although media corporations including CBS, the BBC, VEVO, Hulu, and other organizations offer some of their material via the site, as part of the YouTube partnership program. Unregistered users can watch videos, while registered users can upload an unlimited number of videos. Videos considered to contain potentially offensive content are available only to registered users at least 18 years old.

Use

In this case, it is foreseen that multimedia material related to the project findings should be made available, so a Youtube channel could become the video broadcasting platform for the project: on the one hand, providing of video capabilities to the CLUSTERS 2.0 website. On the other, as an additional starting point for the audience, by using the right terms for the search.

Other multimedia platforms are also available, including Vimeo.

Even, the videos could be stored and played locally in the website. However, although covering the basic functionality, it will lack of the networking promotion and search, that Youtube is covering perfectly at this time.

As said before, the multimedia contents provided in the video platform should be also promoted on the other communication tools.

6. Conclusion

Production of Dissemination Materials is a part of an overall dissemination strategy. It should assist project partners when presenting the project concept and making CLUSTERS 2.0 recognizable among logistics stakeholders. It should complete dissemination actions with CLUSTERS 2.0 identity as communicated and the way the partners want it to be perceived. It aims to create this consistency in the project identity and vision.

In general, Project Dissemination Materials should provide general knowledge about CLUSTERS 2.0, its objectives and concept, make the brand recognizable. It is assumed as supporting tool to build a path to the website where the details on the project and its progress are presented.

To attract target stakeholders multiple dissemination actions are needed. We assume availability of dissemination materials complementary when pursuing other dissemination actions such as external meetings with stakeholders, presentations at conferences, fairs, seminars.

However, we assume these tools relevant and of high support for the promotion of CLUSTERS 2.0.

7. Annexes

7.1 Annex I – Press release example

Press Release

Logo of Partner

Clusters 2.0 will leverage the potential of European Logistics Clusters for a sustainable, efficient and fully integrated transport system.

To do this, it will use an Open Network of Logistics Clusters operating in the frame of Ten-T and supporting local, regional and European development, while keeping neutral the local impacts such as congestion, noise, land use and local pollution levels.

Dourges, 15th May 2017

Today, Clusters 2.0 project has initiate their activities: almost 30 different European companies and institutions have gathered in the premises of Euralogistic - CCI Artois, at Dourges, France, to share and discuss the activities and expectations around this ambitious action, aimed to empower the logistics hubs of Europe into a leading position in terms efficiency and performance while considering the social and environmental impact of logistics.

Logistics clusters become value creators for the regions where they are formed, where a mix of good intermodal connections, logistics platforms and large freight volumes are in place - as in the case of Zaragoza (PLAZA), Duisburg (Duisport), Lille (Dourges), Bologna (Interporto) or London (Heathrow). Once the logistics cluster is well established, the scale creates a virtuous circle building increasing availability of intermodal connections and value added services: co-packing, late product differentiation, vehicle fill optimization and last-mile connections with cities. Time to market, transportation and handling costs are improved and overall emissions and energy utilization reduced. Mature logistics clusters represent an asset for their specific region, as they are growth, employment and competitiveness generators, strengthening economic and social status.

However, well-established logistics clusters still do not leverage their full potentials in terms of competitiveness and sustainability for the European industry and society, due to several reasons:

- Not enough coordination between the local actors in the cluster,
- Not enough connectivity and coordination between European logistics clusters to maximize the full network potential of the clusters and related hubs.

Moreover, logistics clusters also need to deal and minimize negative impacts such as congestion, noise, land use and local pollution.

"If we want to reach the EU objective on modal shift for all transportation beyond 300 km and attract and strengthen competitiveness of local industries at the same time, we need to drive the development of an open collaborative network of hyper connected logistics multimodal clusters building on Ten-T", in words of the project consensus.

During the next 3 years, the project will deploy challenging activities to meet important objectives, such as:

- Increase the engagement, performance and coordination of terminals and hubs in the clusters.
- Achieve a significant step forward in the European Transport performance through a hyper connected network of logistics hubs and clusters.
- Develop low cost, low capital and investment intensive enhanced goods handling and transshipment solutions.

Always applying feasible business models and building robust business plans for the solutions.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723265

Clusters 2.0
Press Release
Logo of Partner

Killer photo: here you can describe your organization and the activities developed in the project (no more than 5-6 sentences - the complete press release should adjust to this page)

Project Factsheet

Duration: 1 May 2017 - 30 April 2020

Total cost: 9.000.000,00€

EC contribution: 6.495.000,00€

Coordinator: PTV Planning Transport Verkeer AG;

Partners: Evidis Solutions S.L.; Measik Factor S.L.; Procter & Gamble Services company NV; Concerto II Innovation; Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V.; Bluewin Strategy S.r.l.; ITT Consulting Srl; Zangiacca Logistics Center; Euratlog/ITC - CC Artoli; Haystack; Menafarke; Kai; Epilacton/Amal; Eperantec; Sabellia; Experia; Pennelements; Eutelsio; Italiani NV; Innovatras Ltd; Van Eck Beerd BV; Treilberg; Hamn AB; Association Pour La Recherche Et Le Développement Des Methodes Et Processus Industriels; Pricer; Constant Terminal S.A.; Heathrow Airport Limited; Air Cargo Belgium; WPS Belgium NV; J.A.M. De Rijck BV; IAG; Global Forwarding Belgium NV; Travelex Post Authority; EgoModel S.L.; CityDepot NV; Argus BV; Union Internationale des Chimistes de Far; Dalsport agency GmbH; University of Antwerp

Contact

Project Coordinator: Marcel Nuchtebeck, PTV Group
marcel.nuchtebeck@ptvgroup.com

Dissemination Coordinator: Francois Nolin, EVIDIS
francois.nolin@evidis.com

Website: <http://www.clusters20.eu>

E-mail: info@clusters20.eu

Twitter: @clusters20_EU

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